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CONTENTS

MECHANISMS FOR IMPLEMENTING TECHNOLOGICAL AND DIGITAL INNOVATIONS.....	10
Shakirxodjayeva Zuxra Rustamxanovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING INVESTMENT PROCESSES IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY	16
Aliyeva Zilola Mamatvalyevna	
CURRENT STATE AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SERVICE SECTORS IN TASHKENT CITY.....	23
Abdikayumov Bekzod Turdiniyozovich	
GREEN BONDS VS. SUSTAINABILITYLINKED LOANS: WHICH WORKS FOR INDUSTRIAL DECARBONISATION?	29
Ataxanov Umidbek Olimovich	
ИНТЕГРИРОВАННАЯ МОДЕЛЬ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТЬЮ БАНКА.....	34
Маликова Дилрабо Муминовна	
ECONOMETRIC MODELLING OF FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	42
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
AN INTEGRAL INDEX METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE INVESTMENT POTENTIAL OF AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES	49
Sayyora Bakhtiyorovna Nazirova	
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЕ, ПУБЛИЧНЫЕ И ОБЩЕСТВЕННЫЕ ФИНАНСЫ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ: ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ГРАНИЦЫ И ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ.....	53
Срождидинова Зарина Хайриддиновна	
BLOCKCHAIN-BASED FINANCIAL TRANSACTION MONITORING SYSTEM (SMART CONTRACTS, DECENTRALIZED DATABASE, AND AUDIT TRAILS).....	58
Olimova Mukhlisa Vohidjon qizi	
FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS A DRIVER OF EMPLOYMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR: REGIONAL DISPARITIES AND INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	65
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN STATISTICAL INDICATORS OF LABOR RESOURCE UTILIZATION IN SURXONDARYO REGION.....	72
Haydarova Dinora Atamurot qizi	
ASSESSING THE ROLE OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES IN REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH ACROSS THE REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN USING INTENSITY COEFFICIENTS AND CLUSTER ANALYSIS.....	77
Anvarkhonov Abdulatifkhon Jamshidkhon ugli	
TECHNICAL, ECONOMIC, AND ENVIRONMENTAL EFFICIENCY OF IMPLEMENTING AGRIVOLTAIC SYSTEMS IN UZBEKISTAN	85
Jabborov Shaymurod Akram o'g'li	
Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li	
Atoyeva Mohinur Amrilloevna	
Avazov Jonibek Azizbek o'g'li	
МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА НА ТРАЕКТОРИЮ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА.....	91
Хазраткулова Лола Нармуминовна	
FINANCING GREEN PROJECTS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN: STATUS, CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS	97

Qorriyeva Shahnoza Safarbayevna

FORMULA-BASED DISTRIBUTION OF INTERGOVERNMENTAL TRANSFERS TO LOCAL BUDGETS IN UZBEKISTAN: A COMPARATIVE SIMULATION ANALYSIS BASED ON 2026 FORECAST INDICATORS.....	103
Umidjon Pardaev	
Sarvar Maxmudov	
GOVERNMENT FUNDING AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES: FINANCIAL PROMOTION MECHANISMS.....	115
Bahriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	
FORECASTING EXPORT AND IMPORT INDICATORS OF BUKHARA REGION	122
Ergashev Mirjon Yorqin o'g'li	
A CUSTOMER-ORIENTED INTEGRATIVE METHODOLOGICAL MODEL FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TOURIST SERVICES IN THE TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY	130
Bakayev Ziyovuddinkhan Toshbolta ogli	
A PESTLI ANALYSIS OF THE EFFICIENCY OF THE HOUSING STOCK MANAGEMENT SYSTEM.....	139
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT STATUS AND EXPORT ACTIVITIES OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN	146
Khikmatullayeva Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi	
CHANGE MANAGEMENT DURING QUALITY ASSURANCE REFORM IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	154
Urinov Bobur Nasilloevich	
СТРАТЕГИИ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ПАЛОМНИЧЕСКОГО ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	162
Каримова Дилафруз Садриддин кизи	
E-COMMERCE AS A DIGITAL FORM OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INCREASING HOUSEHOLD INCOMES.....	167
Eshbayeva Shahnoza Fakhriddinovna	
ADVANTAGES OF IMPLEMENTING AN OCCUPATIONAL AND SKILLS MAPPING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN'S LABOUR MARKET	172
S.B.Goyipnazarov	
S.M.Kurbanbaeva	
ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFICIENCY OF FIXED ASSETS UTILIZATION IN RAILWAY ENTERPRISES: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN.....	178
Turdiyeva Irodaxon Ismoil qizi	
SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO ASSESSING RESOURCE USE IN THE CONTEXT OF A GREEN ECONOMY.....	183
Karimov Islombek Bekpolat o'g'li	
THE IMPACT OF ECOTOURISM ON REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT	
Samiev Siroj Saitovich	
Ochilova Guli Rashid kizi	
THE IMPACT OF RISK ALLOCATION ON INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY IN PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP (PPP) PROJECTS	197
Khaydarova Charos Nizomiddinovna	
PROSPECTS FOR CHANGING THE VOLUME OF GRAPE CULTIVATION DUE TO THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE VITICULTURE COMPLEX.....	202
Boltaev Nazarbek Narzullaevich	
ЦИФРОВЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ОБОСНОВАНИЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ЦЕНЫ В ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЗАКУПКАХ: ПРОЗРАЧНОСТЬ, КОНКУРЕНЦИЯ	

И РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СРЕДСТВ.....	209
Тўхтасинов Бобомурод Исақжон ўғли	
ENHANCING FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT INFLOWS IN THE POST-CRISIS ERA: AN ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF UZBEKISTAN.....	215
Foziljon Rustamov Hazratkulovich	
CURRENT STATE AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY.....	219
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
THE PECULIARITIES OF USING FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TOURIST AND RECREATIONAL AREAS.....	225
Makhliso Umarova	
CHALLENGES OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN HUMAN CAPITAL AND STRATEGIES FOR THEIR RESOLUTION.....	231
Aloviddin Zayniddinov Zayniddin ugli	
ANALYSIS OF THE EXPERIENCE OF SUCCESSFUL AGROTOURISM DESTINATIONS IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES: RECOMMENDATIONS FOR UZBEKISTAN.....	237
Aktamov Olimjon Abdugani o'g'li	
ASSESSING THE EFFICIENCY OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES EXPORT AT THE REGIONAL LEVEL.....	247
Alimova Shamsiya Abidovna	
ECONOMIC ESSENCE OF THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF BUSINESS ENTITIES AND CLASSIFICATION OF THE FACTORS SHAPING IT: THE CASE OF BUKHARA REGION.....	254
Djurayeva Munira Sadillovovna	
THE ROLE OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE ECONOMY OF BUKHARA REGION AND THEIR DEVELOPMENT TRENDS: AN ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL CHANGES AND REGIONAL CONCENTRATION.....	261
Azizjon Anvarovich Kadirov	
Nigina Djurayevna Yusupova	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF BORDER TRANSPORT SYSTEMS.....	268
Ikromov Elyor Ibdulloevich	
ПУТИ ИНТЕГРАЦИИ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ АУДИТОРСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	273
Бобонарова Камола	
GREEN BONDS AND SOVEREIGN DEBT INSTRUMENTS FOR INFRASTRUCTURE ASSET RENEWAL: AN ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL MECHANISMS.....	278
Suleimanov Farrukh	
ENHANCING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL EXPERIENCES.....	286
Qudratova Gulzoda Mahmudovna	
THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SERVICES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	291
Munisa Abdurakhmonova	
ECONOMETRIC MODELING OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH BASED ON THE COBBDOUGLAS PRODUCTION FUNCTION: A CASE STUDY OF SURXONDARYA REGION.....	296
Turaev Bakhtiyor Ergashevich	
GENERAL APPROACHES TO COST REDUCTION IN THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY.....	302
Kamola Saidova	

СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ПЛАНИРОВАНИЯ И ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ВНУТРЕННЕГО АУДИТА В БЮДЖЕТНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ.....	307
Саитмуратов Саитмурат Машарип угли	
A CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF THE IMPACT OF INTERMEDIATION SERVICES ON BANK PERFORMANCE AND ITS STATISTICAL RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.....	314
Miraxmedov Jasur Isroilovich	
EMPLOYER BRANDING IN UZBEKISTAN: HOW TO BECOME AN EMPLOYER OF CHOICE FOR TALENT	320
Doniyorova Fotimabonu Alisher qizi	
FORMING THE COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF MANAGING PERSONNEL AND STUDENTS BASED ON A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH.....	325
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
MODERN APPROACHES TO FORMING A COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.....	331
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
IMPROVEMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF ACCOUNTING AND ANALYSIS OF MATERIAL COSTS IN OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY ENTITIES BASED ON MODERN MANAGEMENT REQUIREMENTS.....	336
Sa'dullayeva Sayyora Nasillo qizi	
ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC APPROACHES AND BARRIERS TO THE INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	341
Samieva Gulnoza Tokhirovna	
THE IMPACT OF EFFECTIVE UTILIZATION OF LABOR POTENTIAL ON THE SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF A REGION (A case study of the Khorezm region).....	348
Kutlimuratov Mansurbek Sattarovich	
CHARACTERISTICS OF CLUSTERING TEXTILE ENTERPRISES.....	354
Asadbek Eshniyozov	
THE ROLE OF EDUCATION AND CAPACITYBUILDING IN DEVELOPING THE ISLAMIC FINANCE INDUSTRY: A THEORETICAL AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS	358
Abdullaev Azamat Akbar o'g'li	
THE ROLE OF 5G TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE OF TELECOMMUNICATION ENTERPRISES	366
Saidqosimova Umida Ibragimovna	
DIGITAL PLATFORMS AND THE EFFICIENCY OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	371
Kholmonov Shodiyor Karshiboyevich	

DIGITAL PLATFORMS AND THE EFFICIENCY OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This study examines the role of digital education platforms in improving the efficiency of inclusive education services in the Republic of Uzbekistan, with particular attention to higher education institutions. As digital transformation reshapes the delivery of educational services, accessible online platforms have become a strategic tool for ensuring equal learning opportunities for students with disabilities and other groups with special educational needs. The research analyzes the current state of digital inclusive education, evaluates the economic efficiency of platform implementation using the Cost–Benefit Analysis (CBA) methodology, and introduces composite indicators—the Student Satisfaction Index (S-Index) and the Digital Inclusion Index (D-Inclusion Index)—to assess service quality. Using the case of Tashkent State University of Economics and its integration with the national HEMIS system, the findings show that the introduction of an inclusive digital platform equipped with sign-language interpretation, content visualization, and adaptive proctoring modules increased the economic efficiency of educational services by approximately 5–6 percent, while improving accessibility and learner satisfaction. The results confirm that the systematic implementation of inclusive digital platforms, supported by reliable indicators and effective policy measures, is essential for the sustainable modernization of higher education and the expansion of equitable access to knowledge in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: digital education platforms, inclusive education, educational services, efficiency, digital economy, cost–benefit analysis, HEMIS, digital inclusion, student satisfaction, Uzbekistan.

Аннотация. В данном исследовании рассматривается роль цифровых образовательных платформ в повышении эффективности инклюзивных образовательных услуг в Республике Узбекистан, с особым акцентом на систему высшего образования. В условиях цифровой трансформации образовательной сферы доступные онлайн-платформы становятся важным инструментом обеспечения равных возможностей обучения для студентов с инвалидностью и других категорий обучающихся с особыми образовательными потребностями. В работе анализируется текущее состояние цифрового инклюзивного образования, оценивается экономическая эффективность внедрения платформ на основе методологии анализа затрат и выгод (Cost–Benefit Analysis, CBA), а также предлагаются интегральные показатели — Индекс удовлетворенности студентов (S-Index) и Индекс цифровой инклюзии (D-Inclusion Index) — для оценки качества образовательных услуг. На примере Ташкентского государственного экономического университета и его интеграции с национальной системой HEMIS установлено, что внедрение инклюзивной цифровой платформы, оснащенной модулями сурдоперевода, визуализации контента и адаптивного прокторинга, позволило повысить экономическую эффективность образовательных услуг примерно на 5–6 %, а также улучшить доступность образования и удовлетворенность обучающихся. Полученные результаты подтверждают, что системное внедрение инклюзивных цифровых платформ, подкрепленное надежными индикаторами и эффективными мерами государственной политики, является важным условием устойчивой модернизации высшего образования и расширения равного доступа к знаниям в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: цифровые образовательные платформы, инклюзивное образование, образовательные услуги, эффективность, цифровая экономика, анализ затрат и выгод, HEMIS, цифровая инклюзия, удовлетворенность студентов, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

Digital transformation has become one of the most influential forces reshaping modern education systems. The rapid development of information and communication technologies, online learning platforms, artificial intelligence, and data-driven management has fundamentally changed the way educational services are designed, delivered, and evaluated. In this context, education is increasingly regarded not only as a social good, but also as an economic service whose quality, accessibility, and efficiency can be measured, modelled, and improved. As economies move toward knowledge-based development models, investment in digital educational infrastructure has become a strategic priority for both developed and developing countries.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the modernisation of the education sector occupies a central place in the national development strategy. The “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” strategy, together with reforms in higher education, has accelerated the adoption of digital platforms, electronic management systems, and online learning environments. The introduction of the Higher Education Management Information System (HEMIS) has created a unified digital foundation for managing the educational process, monitoring quality, and integrating new digital services. These developments have established favourable conditions for expanding the scope and improving the efficiency of educational services across the country.

At the same time, ensuring inclusive education—equal and effective access to learning for students with disabilities and other groups with special educational needs—remains an important task. Traditional educational services do not always fully provide adequate accessibility, individualised support, and flexible learning conditions for such learners. Digital platforms, when designed with inclusive features such as sign-language interpretation, visual adaptation, screen-reader compatibility, and adaptive assessment, offer significant potential to reduce this gap. Consequently, the efficiency of inclusive education services depends not only on the availability of technology, but also on how systematically and economically it is implemented.

This article aims to analyse the current state of digital inclusive education in Uzbekistan, assess the economic efficiency of implementing inclusive digital education platforms, and propose measurable indicators and policy directions for improving the quality of inclusive educational services. The study is grounded in the perspective of the digital economy, treating inclusive education as a measurable service whose efficiency can be enhanced through targeted digital investment and evidence-based management.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The economic and social importance of education has long been recognized in scholarly literature. Human capital theory, developed by Schultz and Becker, established that investment in education directly contributes to productivity, income growth, and economic development. Building on this foundation, later studies emphasized the role of knowledge, information, and technology as primary drivers of modern economic performance, framing education as a key sector of the service economy. These perspectives provide the theoretical basis for analyzing educational services in economic and efficiency-oriented terms.

The impact of digital transformation on services, including education, has been widely examined. Brynjolfsson and McAfee (2014) argued that digital technologies fundamentally change the production and delivery of services by reducing costs, increasing efficiency, and enabling new models of value creation. In the educational context, numerous studies have demonstrated that e-learning and digital platforms can improve access, personalization, and scalability of learning, while also raising issues related to quality assurance and the digital divide. The OECD and UNESCO have repeatedly highlighted that technology alone does not guarantee better outcomes; its effectiveness depends on pedagogical design, infrastructure, and equitable access.

Inclusive education has received particular attention in international policy and research. The United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and UNESCO frameworks emphasize the right to inclusive, equitable, and quality education for all learners. Accessibility standards, such as the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG), provide technical criteria for designing digital learning environments that are usable by people with diverse abilities. However, much of the existing literature focuses on pedagogical and social dimensions, while comparatively fewer studies systematically evaluate the economic efficiency of inclusive digital platforms or propose quantitative indicators for measuring their impact.

In Uzbekistan and other countries of the region, research on the digital economy of education is still emerging. Regional scholars have examined digitalization, e-government, and the development of educational information systems; however, the intersection of inclusive education, digital platforms,

and economic efficiency remains insufficiently explored. This gap highlights the need for an integrated approach that combines digital service design with economic evaluation, which constitutes the central contribution of the present study.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is based on a combination of quantitative, descriptive, and case-study research methods. Statistical and institutional data on the development of digital education in Uzbekistan for the period 2023–2025 were collected from official sources, including the Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovations, and the HEMIS system. The collected data were analyzed using comparative and structural methods.

To evaluate the economic efficiency of implementing an inclusive digital education platform, the Cost–Benefit Analysis (CBA) methodology was applied. CBA compares the total costs of platform development, integration, and operation with quantifiable benefits, including reduced cost per student, time savings, and expanded service coverage.

In addition, two composite indicators were developed and tested in a case study at Tashkent State University of Economics: the Student Satisfaction Index (S-Index), which measures learner satisfaction with accessibility and service quality on a normalized scale, and the Digital Inclusion Index (D-Inclusion Index), which evaluates the extent to which the platform provides equal access for learners with special educational needs.

The combination of these methods makes it possible to assess both the economic and qualitative dimensions of inclusive educational services.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The Republic of Uzbekistan has made significant progress in digitalizing its higher education system. The nationwide deployment of the HEMIS platform has unified the management of academic processes, enrollment, assessment, and quality monitoring across higher education institutions, creating a stable digital infrastructure on which additional services can be built. This foundation is particularly important for inclusive education, as it enables the integration of specialized accessibility modules into an already functioning national system rather than relying on isolated and fragmented solutions.

Despite this progress, the analysis shows that inclusive functionality remains insufficiently developed within most existing digital learning environments. Standard platforms typically provide general access to learning materials but lack dedicated features for learners with hearing, visual, or other impairments. As a result, students with special educational needs may continue to face barriers related to content perception, communication, and assessment. This indicates a substantial gap between the overall level of digitalization and the actual accessibility of educational services for all learners.

To address this gap, the study examines the conceptual model of an inclusive digital education platform, conditionally named “Uyg'on Ta'lim,” designed for integration with the national HEMIS system. The platform combines universal learning functionality with specialized inclusive modules: a sign-language interpretation module for learners with hearing impairments, a content visualization and adaptation module for improved perception, an adaptive online assessment and proctoring module, and accessibility settings compliant with international standards. By integrating these modules into HEMIS rather than operating them separately, the platform reduces duplication of infrastructure and administrative costs while extending accessible services to a wider range of learners.

The economic evaluation based on Cost–Benefit Analysis demonstrates that the systematic implementation of the inclusive platform yields measurable efficiency gains. According to the case-study calculations conducted at Tashkent State University of Economics, the introduction of integrated inclusive digital services increased the economic efficiency of educational service provision by approximately 5–6 percent, primarily through a lower cost per student, reduced reliance on duplicated physical resources, and improved utilization of digital infrastructure. These results confirm that inclusive design, when implemented at the system level, is not only socially beneficial but also economically rational.

Table 1 summarizes the key indicators used to evaluate the efficiency and inclusiveness of digital education services in the case study, along with their interpretation (Table 1).

Table 1
Key Indicators for Evaluating the Efficiency and Inclusiveness of Digital Education Services (Case Study)¹

Indicator	Type	Description
Cost per Student	Economic	Total cost of inclusive service delivery divided by the number of learners served; lower values indicate higher efficiency.
Benefit–Cost Ratio (CBA)	Economic	Ratio of quantifiable benefits to total costs of platform implementation; values above 1 indicate economic viability.
Efficiency Gain	Economic	Improvement in service efficiency after platform integration; estimated at approximately 5–6% in the case study.
Student Satisfaction Index (S-Index)	Quality	Normalized measure of learner satisfaction with accessibility, flexibility, and overall service quality.
Digital Inclusion Index (D-Inclusion)	Quality	Degree of equal access for learners with special educational needs relative to other learners.
Service Coverage	Access	Share of learners, including those with disabilities, able to access inclusive digital services.
Module Utilization Rate	Usage	Frequency of use of inclusive modules (sign-language, visualization, adaptive assessment).

The qualitative assessment based on the Student Satisfaction Index (S-Index) and the Digital Inclusion Index (D-Inclusion Index) supports these findings. After the introduction of inclusive modules, learners reported higher levels of satisfaction with accessibility, flexibility, and the quality of digital services. The strongest improvements were observed among students requiring specialized support. The D-Inclusion Index also showed a notable increase in equality of access between learners with and without special educational needs, indicating that the platform significantly narrowed the inclusion gap rather than merely expanding general access (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Comparative levels of accessibility and learner satisfaction before and after the implementation of inclusive digital modules (S-Index and D-Inclusion Index, case study)

Source: Case study results developed by the author.

Figure 1. Comparative levels of accessibility and learner satisfaction before and after the implementation of inclusive digital modules (S-Index and D-Inclusion Index, case study)².

District- and institution-level observations indicate that the benefits of inclusive digital platforms are distributed unevenly and depend strongly on the level of digital infrastructure, staff readiness, and institutional support. Institutions with stronger technical capacity and management commitment achieved higher efficiency

1 author's development
2 author's development

gains and better inclusion outcomes, while those with limited resources required additional investment and capacity-building. This finding highlights the importance of balanced and targeted support to prevent the emergence of new forms of digital inequality within the inclusive education system.

Overall, the analysis demonstrates that digital education platforms can substantially improve both the efficiency and inclusiveness of educational services in Uzbekistan. The dominant role of the national HEMIS infrastructure, combined with specialized inclusive modules and reliable measurement indicators, provides a practical pathway for modernizing higher education. At the same time, institutional disparities and underdeveloped accessibility features underline the need for continued investment, standardization, and policy coordination.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conducted analysis demonstrates that the implementation of inclusive digital education platforms is an effective instrument for improving the efficiency and accessibility of educational services in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The national digital infrastructure, particularly the HEMIS system, provides a solid foundation on which inclusive functionality can be systematically integrated. As a result, digital platforms have become a strategic mechanism for ensuring equal learning opportunities and modernizing the higher education sector.

The study confirms that the introduction of an integrated inclusive platform combining sign-language interpretation, content visualization, and adaptive assessment modules increased the economic efficiency of educational services by approximately 5–6 percent, while also improving learner satisfaction and equality of access for students with special educational needs. The use of the Cost–Benefit Analysis methodology, together with the Student Satisfaction Index and the Digital Inclusion Index, proved effective for evaluating both the economic and qualitative dimensions of inclusive educational services.

At the same time, the findings reveal significant differences in institutional readiness and outcomes, reflecting variations in digital infrastructure, staff capacity, and management support. These disparities highlight the need for balanced and targeted development policies to prevent the emergence of new forms of digital inequality. Based on the results, the following measures are recommended: integrating inclusive accessibility standards into national digital education platforms; supporting institutional capacity-building and staff training; applying standardized indicators such as the S-Index and D-Inclusion Index for continuous quality monitoring; and ensuring sustained investment in inclusive digital infrastructure as part of national education and digital economy strategies.

The systematic implementation of inclusive digital education platforms, supported by reliable economic evaluation and measurable quality indicators, is essential for the sustainable modernization of higher education in Uzbekistan. Such an approach contributes not only to greater efficiency and equity in educational services, but also to the broader goals of inclusive social development and the formation of a knowledge-based digital economy.

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